

Uncertainty analyses of fluoride-salt Molten Salt Reactors: FHR and MSFR

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ABSTRACT

Molten Salt Reactors (MSR) represent an emerging nuclear technology to which much interest is being paid in recent years. MSRs have the particularity that they contain isotopes (e.g. chlorine, fluorine) that are not present in significant amounts in other reactor families. Therefore, these isotopes may have been paid little attention in the past and their known properties may be affected by large uncertainties that can propagate to calculated reactor parameters. In this context, sensitivity and uncertainty (S/U) analyses are of capital importance to identify nuclear data needs associated with these isotopes. In fact, in the case of chloride-salt MSR, uncertainty analyses have identified chlorine as a major contributor to the uncertainty. This has prompted new experimental cross section measurements. However, comparatively less attention has been paid to fluoride MSRs. Furthermore, S/U analyses tend to focus on the multiplication factor (k_{eff}), while the impact of the uncertainty of nuclear data may be different in other reactor parameters. In this work, we present an uncertainty analysis of several parameters of interest of two fluoride MSR designs: a thermal spectrum one (FHR) and a fast spectrum one (MSFR). The uncertainty in the multiplication factor and several reactivity responses (void effect, temperature effects) have been analyzed with covariance matrices from several nuclear data libraries (ENDF/B-8.0, JEFF-4.0 and JENDL-5).

Keywords: nuclear data, uncertainty, MSR, FHR, MSFR

1. INTRODUCTION

Molten Salt Reactors (MSRs) are a family of reactors that is currently receiving a great deal of attention. Their attractive features include the impossibility of core meltdown accidents (the fuel being in a molten state), low-pressure operation and the ability to continuously extract the fuel for reprocessing. However, they also pose major challenges, the most relevant one being maybe the little operating experience with them. From the point of view of nuclear data (ND), they pose the challenge of introducing nuclides in the core that are not present in other reactor families (e.g. fluorine, chlorine). Hence, their properties (cross sections) may have been paid little attention and, therefore, can be affected by large uncertainties that can propagate to important reactor parameters. For this reason, MSR are of particular interest for performing sensitivity and uncertainty (S/U) analyses of nuclear data.

It is important to take into account that MSRs represent a very diverse reactor family that includes many different designs. They differ, among others, in the molten salt (chloride, fluoride), the neutron spectra (thermal, fast) and the fuel cycle (thorium cycle, uranium cycle). The impact of ND uncertainties can therefore be very different in different MSR designs. In this work, we focus on two fluoride-salt MSR designs, for which detailed design information is available: a thermal MSR (graphite-moderated) operating in the uranium cycle and a fast one operating in the thorium cycle. The first one is a Fluoride salt-cooled High-temperature Reactors (FHR) used in the OECD/NEA benchmark of the same name, which is based in the Advanced High-Temperature Reactor (AHTR) design developed at ORNL [1, 2]. The second one is the Molten Salt Fast Reactor (MSFR), developed by CNRS [3].

It may be worth mentioning here that, since fluorine has overall a smaller cross sections than chlorine (considering all isotopes), the impact of their associated uncertainties in reactor parameters is also expected to be lower. Possibly for this reason, S/U analyses in fluoride-salt MSRs have been paid less attention, in our opinion, than in chloride-salt MSRs. In these last ones, S/U analyses have allowed identifying, in particular, the reaction $^{35}\text{Cl}(n,p)$ as major source of uncertainty. This has prompted new

experimental measurements [4,5]. Nevertheless, as will be shown later, the impact of the ND uncertainty in fluoride-salt MSR designs can still be large enough to exceed typical target accuracy requirements of important reactor parameters, hence our motivation for this work.

This work is structured as follows: the systems analyzed (FHR and MSFR) are briefly described in section 2. The methodology followed, consisting in combining sensitivity calculations with the MCNP code [6] with covariance matrices from several nuclear data libraries, is described in section 3. Finally, the uncertainty results are presented in section 4. The parameters analyzed in both systems are the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}), the fuel Doppler coefficient and the molten-salt density reactivity effect (full void in the case of FHR).

2. FHR and MSFR

As stated above, in this work we have considered two different fluoride-salt MSR designs: a thermal one (FHR) and a fast one (MSFR). The FHR (Figure 1) is a thermal, graphite-moderated, solid-fuel MSR with the fuel in form of TRISO particles dispersed within the graphite moderator blocks, i.e. it is not dissolved in the FLiBe salt, which acts only as coolant. Fuel is uranium 9% enriched in ^{235}U ; the calculations have been performed in a begin-of-cycle state with no fuel burnup. Burnable poisons in the shape of Eu_2O_3 spheres are also present. The core consists of 168 hexagonal fuel elements, its dimensions are approx. 4×4 m (diameter \times height) and it is surrounded by radial and axial graphite reflectors. The MCNP model used in this work has been developed considering the latest benchmark specifications, including a reduced core height and a smaller number of fuel elements [7].

The MSFR, for its part, is a fast MSR design featuring liquid fuel. A schematic of the MCNP model used in this work is presented in Figure 2. It operates in the thorium cycle and variants considering cores using either ^{233}U or irradiated uranium fuel as initial fissile materials have been developed. The calculations presented in this work consider the first case. As in the FHR, the S/U calculations presented in this work have been performed in a begin-of-cycle state with no fuel burnup. The core is surrounded by a breeding blanket with ^{232}Th also dissolved in a FLiBe salt. A simplified model of a B₄C structure to protect the heat exchangers is also present in the model. Finally, the whole system is surrounded by a reflector made up of a Ni-based alloy.

3. SUMMON

The methodology followed in this work to propagate the ND uncertainty to reactor parameters consists in calculating sensitivity profiles with the MCNP code (KSEN card) and combine them with covariance matrices from different nuclear data libraries using the so-called “sandwich rule”. In this way, the ND uncertainty (variance) of a given reactor parameter k is given by:

$$\text{Var}(k) = \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial k}{\partial \alpha_i} \right)^2 \text{Var}(\alpha_i) + \sum_{i,j} \frac{\partial k}{\partial \alpha_i} \frac{\partial k}{\partial \alpha_j} \text{Cov}(\alpha_i, \alpha_j) = \vec{s}V\vec{s}^T \quad (1)$$

Where $V = \text{Cov}(\alpha_i, \alpha_j)$ is the covariance matrix of the input parameters α_i (which, in this case, usually refers to the neutron cross section in a given energy range) and \vec{s} is the sensitivity profile, i.e. the vector of the (relative) sensitivity coefficients $s_{\alpha_i} = \partial k / \partial \alpha_i$.

This process has been implemented in the SUMMON (Sensitivity and Uncertainty Methodology for MONTEcarlo codes) code developed at CIEMAT [8]. Very briefly, the steps taken by SUMMON to calculate ND uncertainties are the following: (1) Read k_{eff} sensitivity profiles (in a number of energy groups), calculated with MCNP or other Monte Carlo code, from SDF-formatted files. (2) In the case of reactivity responses (i.e. reactivity differences between two reactor configurations), automatically compute their sensitivity profiles. (3) Read BOXER-formatted covariance matrices. (4) If the sensitivity profiles and covariance matrices have different energy group structures, collapse the sensitivity profiles to the covariance matrix energy group structure. (5) Apply Eq. 1 to calculate the ND uncertainty, both the total value and the contributions of individual isotope-reactions and energy groups.

In a previous work, SUMMON has been verified against ND uncertainty results obtained with the fully stochastic SANDY code [9]. It is also worth mentioning that SUMMON also allows propagating the

statistical (Monte Carlo) uncertainty present in the sensitivity profiles. A correct evaluation of this statistical uncertainty in the ND uncertainty is of particular importance in the case of scattering reactions, since they calculated sensitivity profiles are usually affected by large statistical uncertainties, which can result in an overestimation of the nuclear data uncertainty introduced by these reactions [10]. Hence, all ND uncertainty figures presented in section 4 are accompanied by their corresponding statistical uncertainty estimate.

All sensitivity calculations have been performed with the JEFF-3.3 library. These results have been combined with covariance matrices of the ENDF/B-8.0, JEFF-4.0¹ and JENDL-5 nuclear data libraries. These have been processed at CIEMAT with the NJOY21 code [11] in the ECCO-33 energy group structure, for the case of the MSFR, and the SHEM 281 energy group structure [12], for the case of the FHR.

Figure 1. Schematics of the MCNP FHR model used in this work.

Figure 2. Schematics of the MCNP MSFR model used in this work.

¹ For this work, ¹⁶O, ¹⁵¹Eu and ¹⁵³Eu have been removed from the JEFF-4.0 covariance matrix set as they resulted in very high uncertainties that may be due to mistakes in the ENDF file and/or the processing.

4. RESULTS

As already mentioned, S/U analysis have been performed for three parameters of the FHR and the MSFR, namely: the multiplication factor (k_{eff}), the Doppler reactivity coefficient and the molten-salt density reactivity effect (full void in the case of FHR). Calculated values of these parameters with their statistical (Monte Carlo) uncertainties and some details of the calculations are summarized in table I.

Table I. Values of the reactor parameters of FHR and MSFR analyzed in this work (in the case of MSFR no statistical uncertainty estimates are provided because they are very small).

		FHR	MSFR
k_{eff}		1.09166 (2)	0.97862
Fuel Doppler	1000 K → 1200 K	-759(2) pcm (total) -3.79(1) pcm/K	-750 pcm (total) -3.75 pcm/K
	1000 K → 2100 K	-3463(3) pcm -3.147(2) pcm/K	---
Molten salt density		-585(3) pcm (full void)	-851 pcm (-5% density)

The results of the ND uncertainty analysis are presented in table II (FHR) and table III (MSFR)³. Notice that the reactions are always listed in pairs. When both reactions are the same, it represents the uncertainty (standard deviation) due to the variance of this reaction (considering the correlations between energy groups). On the other hand, when two reactions are listed, the value represents the contribution to the ND uncertainty of the covariance of this pair of reactions, which can be either positive or negative, as the correlations between reactions can increase or decrease the total ND uncertainty.

4.1. Effective multiplication factor (k_{eff})

Regarding the ND uncertainty in the k_{eff} , in the case of the thermal FHR, it is dominated by the fission ν of ^{235}U with all three covariance matrix sets utilized (ENDF/B-8.0, JEFF-4.0 and JENDL-5). The difference between these sets lays in the total value of this uncertainty and how it is shared between the prompt and total components and the covariance between them. The next most important contributors to the uncertainty are ^7Li (n,γ) and ^{235}U (n,f), the value of their contribution depending on the library (JENDL-5 lacks covariance information on ^7Li). The total value of the uncertainty due to nuclear data in k_{eff} ranges between 0.6 and 1%, or 600 to 1000 pcm, which is a typical value found for many reactor families. These results are in line with published ND uncertainty values in other thermal, fluoride-salt MSR designs [13].

In the case of the fast MSFR, the differences between covariance matrix sets are more relevant. Both the JEFF-4.0 and JENDL-5 covariance matrices result in uncertainties of about 4% or 4000 pcm, although the main contributors are different: in JEFF-4.0 is the ^{233}U (n,f) reaction and in JENDL-5 it is the ^{232}Th (n,γ)⁴. ENDF/B-8.0 contain covariance data for both these reactions but its overall effect is smaller. Still total ND uncertainty in k_{eff} is about 1.8%. As a final comment, the values of the contribution to the

³ Note on the reaction nomenclature: (n,γ) means neutron capture, (n,f) means fission, (n,n) means elastic scattering, (n,n') means inelastic scattering, ν_f is the average number of neutrons per fission (fission number), ν_p is the average number of prompt neutrons per fission and χ_i is the total fission spectrum.

⁴ This is a similar figure to the ~4000 pcm of uncertainty in the k_{eff} due to the ^{35}Cl (n,p) reaction reported in the case of chloride MSRs [4]. It should be noted, however, that this figure was obtained from calculations performed with different versions of the ENDF/B library, not from the information contained in the covariance matrices.

uncertainty to the MSFR k_{eff} for the most relevant reactions ($^{232}\text{Th}(n,\gamma)$, $^{232}\text{Th}(n,n)$, $^{233}\text{U}(n,f)$, $^{233}\text{U}(n,\gamma)$, $^7\text{Li}(n,n)$) obtained in this study are very similar to the ones published in [14].

4.2. Fuel Doppler effect

The ND uncertainty in the Doppler effect in the thermal FHR is dominated by the uncertainty of the $^{238}\text{U}(n,\gamma)$ reaction (ENDF/B-8.0 and JENDL-5), which is understandable given the importance of the neutron captures in this isotope for the Doppler effect. The uncertainty introduced by this reaction takes the same value with all three covariance data sets. With the JEFF-4.0 covariance matrices, however, $^9\text{Be}(n,n)$ turns out to be the major contributor to the ND uncertainty. This result is affected by a large statistical uncertainty, however, so it should be taken with care. The overall value of the uncertainty due to nuclear data is relatively small, about 1-2% with all libraries.

In the case of the MSFR, however, there are major differences between libraries. With ENDF/B-8.0 covariances, ND uncertainty is dominated by reactions in ^{19}F . In the case of JEFF-4.0, the $^{233}\text{U}(n,f)$ reaction (which also had an important effect in the case of k_{eff}) is the most relevant one. With these two libraries, the total uncertainty due to nuclear data is about 20%. Notice that in the MSFR, the temperature of the entire fuel salt is changed, while in the FHR only the fuel temperature was changed. JENDL-5.0 does not contain covariance data for ^{19}F , and therefore the total uncertainty due to nuclear data with this library is much smaller (still about 7%).

4.3. Molten salt density reactivity effect

In the FHR it is remarkable the very large ND uncertainty in the void effect (up to 60%). This large uncertainty is mainly due to the $^7\text{Li}(n,\gamma)$ and, in the case of JEFF-4.0, to $^9\text{Be}(n,n)$. JENDL-5.0 contain no covariance information for these reactions, which results in a much lower value of the total ND uncertainty. The relatively low importance of fuel isotopes cross sections can be explained by the small change in the spectrum due to core voiding, since the spectrum is largely determined by the graphite moderator. Therefore, the major contributors to the ND uncertainty are the isotopes in the FLiBe coolant that disappear with the voiding.

In the case of MSFR, although the results have relatively poor statistics (in this case, only a reduction of 5% in the molten salt density has been performed), it is enough to identify the same tendency that is observed in the k_{eff} and the Doppler coefficient. Hence, reactions in ^{19}F dominate the uncertainty in the case of the ENDF/B-8.0 covariance matrices, reactions in ^{233}U in the case of JEFF-4.0 and reactions in ^{232}Th in the case of JENDL-5. The overall value of ND uncertainty in the molten salt density reactivity effect (<5%) is much smaller than in FHR, though.

As a final comment, it is worth remarking that, as mentioned in section 2, in this work we have only considered systems containing fresh fuel. Since fissile and/or fertile isotopes have turned to be major contributors to the uncertainty in many of the reactor parameters studied, changes in the fuel composition during burnup will likely have a major impact in the uncertainty due to nuclear data.

5. CONCLUSIONS

We have presented the results of a ND uncertainty analysis of several reactor parameters of two molten-salt reactor designs, the thermal FHR and the fast MSFR. Although the results of ND uncertainty calculations depend strongly on the system, the parameter investigated and the covariance matrix set, some general trends can be observed. In the case of the thermal FHR, the ND uncertainty in k_{eff} is dominated by the ^{235}U fission ν . The ND uncertainty in the Doppler effect is dominated by the $^{238}\text{U}(n,\gamma)$ and $^9\text{Be}(n,n)$ (in the case of JEFF-4.0). In the case of the molten salt density effect, ND uncertainty is dominated by the $^7\text{Li}(n,\gamma)$ (ENDF/B-8.0, JEFF-4.0) and $^9\text{Be}(n,n)$ (JEFF-4.0) reactions. Furthermore, in this last parameter, the ND uncertainty is very high (up to 60%).

In the case of the fast MSFR, it is remarkable the uncertainty introduced by the $^{233}\text{U}(n,f)$ cross section in the case of JEFF-4.0 and $^{232}\text{Th}(n,\gamma)$ in the case of JENDL-5. These can result in large values of the ND uncertainty in the k_{eff} (up to about 4% or 4000 pcm) and the Doppler coefficient (up to about 20%). ^{19}F cross section uncertainties were also a major source of uncertainty in all three parameters investigated.

Overall, we consider that the value of the ND uncertainties found in this work are high enough to recommend that they are taken into account in the design of MSRs. These findings also underline the need for continuous improvement of nuclear data.

Table IIIa. Major contributors to the uncertainty of FHR k_{eff} .

(a) ENDF/B-8.0			(b) JEFF-4.0			(c) JENDL-5.0		
Quantity		Unc (%)	Quantity		Unc (%)	Quantity		Unc (%)
$^{235}\text{U } \nu_t$	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_p$	0.64623(16)	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_p$	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_p$	0.55562(13)	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_t$	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_p$	0.41730(10)
$^{235}\text{U } \nu_t$	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_t$	0.45784(11)	$^7\text{Li } (n,\gamma)$	$^7\text{Li } (n,\gamma)$	0.29395(3)	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_t$	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_t$	0.29591(7)
$^{235}\text{U } \nu_p$	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_p$	0.45697(25)	$^{235}\text{U } (n,f)$	$^{235}\text{U } (n,f)$	0.27121(17)	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_p$	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_p$	0.29505(7)
$^7\text{Li } (n,\gamma)$	$^7\text{Li } (n,\gamma)$	0.29395(3)	$^{235}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	$^{235}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	0.260406(26)	$^{235}\text{U } (n,f)$	$^{235}\text{U } (n,f)$	0.17898(12)
$^{235}\text{U } (n,f)$	$^{235}\text{U } (n,f)$	0.17905(12)	$^9\text{Be } (n,n)$	$^9\text{Be } (n,n)$	0.235(8)	$^{238}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	$^{238}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	0.13180(6)
$^{238}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	$^{238}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	0.13175(6)	$^{238}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	$^{238}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	0.13181(6)	$^{235}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	$^{235}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	0.056026(6)
$^{153}\text{Eu } (n,\gamma)$	$^{153}\text{Eu } (n,\gamma)$	0.06661(9)	$^9\text{Be } (n,n)$	$^9\text{Be } (n,\gamma)$	-0.088(2)	$^{238}\text{U } (n,n)$	$^{238}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	0.0558(7)
$^{235}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	$^{235}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	0.056322(6)	$^{235}\text{U } (n,f)$	$^{235}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	-0.08330(19)	$^{238}\text{U } (n,n)$	$^{238}\text{U } (n,n)$	0.0516(4)
Total		0.99683(25)	Total		0.780(3)	Total		0.63843(17)

Table IIIb. Major contributors to the uncertainty of FHR Doppler reactivity coefficient (1000 to 2100 K).

(a) ENDF/B-8.0			(b) JEFF-4.0			(c) JENDL-5.0		
Quantity		Unc (%)	Quantity		Unc (%)	Quantity		Unc (%)
$^{238}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	$^{238}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	0.6945(28)	$^9\text{Be } (n,n)$	$^9\text{Be } (n,n)$	1.4(3)	$^{238}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	$^{238}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	0.6945(28)
$^{235}\text{U } \nu_t$	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_p$	0.641(6)	$^{238}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	$^{238}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	0.6945(28)	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_t$	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_p$	0.399(4)
$^{235}\text{U } \nu_t$	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_t$	0.454(4)	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_p$	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_p$	0.553(5)	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_t$	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_t$	0.2829(28)
$^{235}\text{U } \nu_p$	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_p$	0.454(4)	$^{235}\text{U } (n,f)$	$^{235}\text{U } (n,f)$	0.350(7)	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_p$	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_p$	0.2821(28)
$^7\text{Li } (n,\gamma)$	$^7\text{Li } (n,\gamma)$	0.2847(12)	$^7\text{Li } (n,\gamma)$	$^7\text{Li } (n,\gamma)$	0.2847(12)	$^{238}\text{U } (n,n)$	$^{238}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	0.24(4)
$^{238}\text{U } (n,n)$	$^{238}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	0.24(3)	$^{238}\text{U } (n,n)$	$^{238}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	0.24(3)	$^{235}\text{U } (n,f)$	$^{235}\text{U } (n,f)$	0.180(5)
$^{19}\text{F } (n,n)$	$^{19}\text{F } (n,n)$	0.24(6)	$^{19}\text{F } (n,n)$	$^{19}\text{F } (n,n)$	0.23(6)	$^{238}\text{U } (n,n)$	$^{238}\text{U } (n,n)$	0.119(15)
$^{235}\text{U } (n,f)$	$^{235}\text{U } (n,f)$	0.181(5)	$^{235}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	$^{235}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	0.2280(10)	$^{235}\text{U } \chi_t$	$^{235}\text{U } \chi_t$	0.064(27)
Total		1.265(26)	Total		1.8(3)	Total		0.957(6)

Table IIIc. Major contributors to the uncertainty of FHR reactivity void worth (full void).

(a) ENDF/B-8.0			(b) JEFF-4.0			(c) JENDL-5.0		
Quantity		Unc (%)	Quantity		Unc (%)	Quantity		Unc (%)
$^7\text{Li } (n,\gamma)$	$^7\text{Li } (n,\gamma)$	46.01(3)	$^7\text{Li } (n,\gamma)$	$^7\text{Li } (n,\gamma)$	46.01(3)	$^{235}\text{U } \chi_t$	$^{235}\text{U } \chi_t$	2.24(21)
$^{19}\text{F } (n,\gamma)$	$^{19}\text{F } (n,\gamma)$	6.407(5)	$^9\text{Be } (n,n)$	$^9\text{Be } (n,n)$	36.9(12)	$^{235}\text{U } (n,f)$	$^{235}\text{U } (n,f)$	1.916(24)
$^7\text{Li } (n,n)$	$^7\text{Li } (n,n)$	5.52(25)	$^9\text{Be } (n,n)$	$^9\text{Be } (n,\gamma)$	-13.8(3)	$^{238}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	$^{238}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	1.818(13)
$^{19}\text{F } (n,n)$	$^{19}\text{F } (n,n)$	4.76(22)	$^9\text{Be } (n,\gamma)$	$^9\text{Be } (n,\gamma)$	8.606(6)	$^{235}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	$^{235}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	1.2497(23)
$^{19}\text{F } (n,\alpha)$	$^{19}\text{F } (n,\alpha)$	2.877(5)	$^{19}\text{F } (n,\gamma)$	$^{19}\text{F } (n,\gamma)$	6.407(5)	$^{238}\text{U } (n,n)$	$^{238}\text{U } (n,n)$	0.98(10)
$^{235}\text{U } (n,f)$	$^{235}\text{U } (n,f)$	1.925(24)	$^7\text{Li } (n,n)$	$^7\text{Li } (n,n)$	5.52(25)	$^{238}\text{U } (n,n)$	$^{238}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	0.86(14)
$^6\text{Li } (n,t)$	$^6\text{Li } (n,t)$	1.8777(13)	$^{19}\text{F } (n,n)$	$^{19}\text{F } (n,n)$	4.76(22)	$^{235}\text{U } (n,f)$	$^{235}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	-0.691(7)
$^{238}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	$^{238}\text{U } (n,\gamma)$	1.814(13)	$^{235}\text{U } \chi_t$	$^{235}\text{U } \chi_t$	4.2(3)	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_t$	$^{235}\text{U } \nu_p$	0.490(10)
Total		47.42(7)	Total		59.3(11)	Total		3.94(17)

Table IVa. Major contributors to the uncertainty of U-started MSFR k_{eff} .

(a) ENDF/B-8.0			(b) JEFF-4.0			(c) JENDL-5.0		
Quantity		Unc (%)	Quantity		Unc (%)	Quantity		Unc (%)
$^{232}\text{Th} (n,\gamma)$	$^{232}\text{Th} (n,\gamma)$	1.34046(7)	$^{233}\text{U} (n,f)$	$^{233}\text{U} (n,f)$	4.0602(4)	$^{232}\text{Th} (n,\gamma)$	$^{232}\text{Th} (n,\gamma)$	3.76018(15)
$^{233}\text{U} v_t$	$^{233}\text{U} v_p$	0.679130(20)	$^{232}\text{Th} (n,\gamma)$	$^{232}\text{Th} (n,\gamma)$	1.33555(7)	$^{233}\text{U} v_t$	$^{233}\text{U} v_p$	0.679130(20)
$^{233}\text{U} (n,\gamma)$	$^{233}\text{U} (n,\gamma)$	0.553358(11)	$^{233}\text{U} v_t$	$^{233}\text{U} v_p$	0.535878(18)	$^{233}\text{U} (n,\gamma)$	$^{233}\text{U} (n,\gamma)$	0.553513(11)
$^{233}\text{U} v_t$	$^{233}\text{U} v_t$	0.480681(14)	$^{233}\text{U} (n,\gamma)$	$^{233}\text{U} (n,\gamma)$	0.451826(6)	$^{233}\text{U} v_t$	$^{233}\text{U} v_t$	0.480681(14)
$^{233}\text{U} v_p$	$^{233}\text{U} v_p$	0.480249(14)	$^{233}\text{U} v_t$	$^{233}\text{U} v_t$	0.379883(13)	$^{233}\text{U} v_p$	$^{233}\text{U} v_p$	0.480249(14)
$^{233}\text{U} (n,f)$	$^{233}\text{U} (n,f)$	0.341134(20)	$^{233}\text{U} v_p$	$^{233}\text{U} v_p$	0.378938(13)	$^{233}\text{U} (n,f)$	$^{233}\text{U} (n,f)$	0.418160(22)
$^7\text{Li} (n,n)$	$^7\text{Li} (n,n)$	0.11582(21)	$^{233}\text{U} (n,n)$	$^{233}\text{U} (n,f)$	0.367(4)	$^{232}\text{Th} (n,n)$	$^{232}\text{Th} (n,n)$	0.3310(7)
$^{232}\text{Th} (n,n)$	$^{232}\text{Th} (n,n)$	0.09156(18)	$^7\text{Li} (n,n)$	$^7\text{Li} (n,n)$	0.1158(2)	$^{232}\text{Th} (n,f)$	$^{232}\text{Th} (n,f)$	0.0414326(20)
Total		1.78294(8)	Total		4.3842(6)	Total		3.95695(22)

Table IVb. Major contributors to the uncertainty of U-started MSFR Doppler reactivity coefficient (1000 to 1200 K).

(a) ENDF/B-8.0			(b) JEFF-4.0			(c) JENDL-5.0		
Quantity		Unc (%)	Quantity		Unc (%)	Quantity		Unc (%)
$^{19}\text{F} (n,n)$	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n)$	11.03(4)	$^{233}\text{U} (n,f)$	$^{233}\text{U} (n,f)$	12.65(10)	$^{232}\text{Th} (n,\gamma)$	$^{232}\text{Th} (n,\gamma)$	7.81(4)
$^{19}\text{F} (n,n')$	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n')$	9.35(5)	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n)$	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n)$	11.08(4)	$^{233}\text{U} (n,f)$	$^{233}\text{U} (n,f)$	1.216(5)
$^{19}\text{F} (n,\alpha)$	$^{19}\text{F} (n,\alpha)$	8.1857(10)	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n')$	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n')$	9.03(5)	$^{232}\text{Th} (n,n)$	$^{232}\text{Th} (n,n)$	1.10(20)
$^{19}\text{F} (n,n\alpha)$	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n\alpha)$	4.7070(12)	$^{19}\text{F} (n,\alpha)$	$^{19}\text{F} (n,\alpha)$	8.1857(10)	$^{233}\text{U} v_t$	$^{233}\text{U} v_p$	0.643(5)
$^{19}\text{F} (n,n)$	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n')$	4.36(12)	$^{19}\text{F} (n,\alpha)$	$^{19}\text{F} (n,\alpha)$	4.7070(12)	$^{233}\text{U} v_t$	$^{233}\text{U} v_t$	0.456(3)
$^{19}\text{F} (n,n')$	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n\alpha)$	-3.757(14)	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n)$	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n')$	4.32(9)	$^{233}\text{U} v_p$	$^{233}\text{U} v_p$	0.455(3)
$^{19}\text{F} (n,n)$	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n\alpha)$	2.399(21)	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n')$	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n\alpha)$	-3.757(14)	$^{233}\text{U} (n,\gamma)$	$^{233}\text{U} (n,\gamma)$	0.4404(21)
$^{232}\text{Th} (n,\gamma)$	$^{232}\text{Th} (n,\gamma)$	2.358(13)	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n)$	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n\alpha)$	2.396(21)	$^{233}\text{U} \chi_t$	$^{233}\text{U} \chi_t$	0.298(24)
Total		18.01(5)	Total		21.80(9)	Total		8.05(6)

Table IVc. Major contributors to the uncertainty of U-started MSFR reactivity void worth (-5% fuel salt density).

(a) ENDF/B-8.0			(b) JEFF-4.0			(c) JENDL-5.0		
Quantity		Unc (%)	Quantity		Unc (%)	Quantity		Unc (%)
$^{19}\text{F} (n,n)$	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n)$	1.33(6)	$^{233}\text{U} (n,f)$	$^{233}\text{U} (n,f)$	4.19(7)	$^{232}\text{Th} (n,n)$	$^{232}\text{Th} (n,n)$	1.54(15)
$^{233}\text{U} v_t$	$^{233}\text{U} v_p$	0.653(4)	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n)$	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n)$	1.38(7)	$^{232}\text{Th} (n,\gamma)$	$^{232}\text{Th} (n,\gamma)$	1.266(24)
$^{19}\text{F} (n,n')$	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n')$	0.63(4)	$^{233}\text{U} (n,n)$	$^{233}\text{U} (n,f)$	-1.04(25)	$^{233}\text{U} v_t$	$^{233}\text{U} v_p$	0.653(4)
$^{19}\text{F} (n,n)$	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n')$	-0.61(6)	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n)$	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n')$	-0.71(5)	$^{233}\text{U} (n,f)$	$^{233}\text{U} (n,f)$	0.648(4)
$^{232}\text{Th} (n,\gamma)$	$^{232}\text{Th} (n,\gamma)$	0.582(10)	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n')$	$^{19}\text{F} (n,n')$	0.66(4)	$^{233}\text{U} v_t$	$^{233}\text{U} v_t$	0.4624(25)
$^{233}\text{U} (n,f)$	$^{233}\text{U} (n,f)$	0.476(3)	$^{232}\text{Th} (n,\gamma)$	$^{232}\text{Th} (n,\gamma)$	0.579(10)	$^{233}\text{U} v_p$	$^{233}\text{U} v_p$	0.4620(25)
$^{233}\text{U} v_t$	$^{233}\text{U} v_t$	0.4624(25)	$^7\text{Li} (n,n)$	$^7\text{Li} (n,n)$	0.46(4)	$^{233}\text{U} \chi_t$	$^{233}\text{U} \chi_t$	0.302(17)
$^7\text{Li} (n,n)$	$^7\text{Li} (n,n)$	0.46(4)	$^{233}\text{U} v_t$	$^{233}\text{U} v_p$	0.429(3)	$^{233}\text{U} (n,\gamma)$	$^{233}\text{U} (n,\gamma)$	0.2253(17)
Total		1.93(7)	Total		4.44(10)	Total		2.35(14)

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